

Full chain cases for SBCC

Report D2.1.2

MS2.1.1 Full chain utilization cases defined.

MS2.1.4 Full chain storage cases defined.

Author: Kristian Aas, Ragnhild Skagestad, Anette Mathisen

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AUTHORISATION	Name	Signature	Date
WP Leader	Ragnhild Skagestad	<i>Ragnhild Skagestad</i>	25/06/2024/YY
Project Coordinator	Marco Linders	<i>Marco Linders</i> <small>Marco Linders (Jan 26, 2024 08:38 GMT+2)</small>	26/06/2024/YY

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Executive summary

This deliverable concentrates on the definition of full chain CCUS cases that will be evaluated in EverLoNG. Definition contains ship types, port location, sailing route, the Ship Based Carbon Capture (SBCC), onshore facilities for CO₂ handling and the transport of CO₂ to either storage or utilization.

The defined cases will be evaluated by life cycle analysis (LCA) and techno-economic assessments (TEA) in WP4.

In EverLoNG two ship types are considered for SBCC and will also be part of the full chain cases.

- The SSCV Sleipnir, the world's largest crane vessel (SSCV: Semi-Submersible Crane Vessel), operated by Heerema Marine Contractors
- A typical LNG tanker ship, operated by Total energies.

The specific ports selected are Port of Houston in Texas and Port of Rotterdam in The Netherlands. Both ports have closeness to infrastructure for CCS, which is identified in this project as the main selection criteria for enabling SBCC full chains. These Ports are also central for the regions.

The sailing route for the LNG tanker ship is defined by the route between Houston and Rotterdam. The sailing route for the SSCV Sleipnir is based on actual operation during an almost 2-year period.

Due to available capacity, the Northern Lights Project is chosen as a storage site in the full chain cases in EverLoNG. An Alternative to Northern Lights is the Aramis project that is planned during the coming years offshore the coast of Netherlands. Even if the Porthos project is located perfectly with respect to EverLoNG offloading of CO₂ in Rotterdam, it is not likely as storage site since it is already fully booked.

Production of methane or methanol, via catalytic processing of captured CO₂ and green hydrogen are chosen as the utilization cases in EverLoNG.

To summarize, four main cases have been suggested:

- Case 1: Sleipnir CO₂ storage pathway
- Case 2: Sleipnir CO₂ utilization pathway
- Case 3: LNG tanker CO₂ storage pathway
- Case 4: LNG tanker CO₂ utilization pathway

For all these cases, two different routes for storage or utilization have been identified. Storage is suggested in connection to the Northern Lights project and the Aramis project. For the cases with utilization pathways, production of methanol or methane has been proposed.

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Background

Ship-Based Carbon Capture (SBCC) is proposed as a low-cost alternative to decarbonize the maritime sector, as compared to zero-emission fuels (ammonia, hydrogen). The objective of the "EverLoNG" project is to accelerate the implementation of the SBCC technology by.

- Demonstrating SBCC on-board of LNG-fuelled ships.
- Optimizing SBCC integration to the existing ship infrastructure.
- Facilitating the development of SBCC-based full CCUS chains.
- Facilitating the regulatory framework for the technology.

This concentrates on the definition of full chain CCUS cases that will be evaluated in the project.

Definition contains ship types, port location, sailing route, the SBCC, onshore facilities for CO₂ handling and the transport of CO₂ to either storage or utilization.

The defined cases will be evaluated by life cycle analysis (LCA) and techno-economic assessments (TEA) in WP4. Port selection is included and will be aligned with task 2.2 "CO₂ shipping interoperability and port readiness". TotalEnergies and Heerema will advise on the ships' ports of call.

Figure 1, show the principle for the full chain in EverLoNG.

Figure 1: Principle for EverLoNG full chain [1].

Ships

In EverLoNG two ship types are considered for SBCC and will also be part of the full chain cases.

More specifically (see Figure 2):

- **The SSCV Sleipnir**, the world’s largest crane vessel (SSCV: Semi-Submersible Crane Vessel), operated by Heerema Marine Contractors
- **A typical LNG tanker ship**, operated by Total energies.

Heerema’s Sleipnir	TOTAL’s LNG carrier *
<p>Type: crane ship Main Power: 96 MW total main power plant, consisting of 12 engines of 8 MW each, divided over four engine rooms (three engines per engine room). Fuel (dual): Low sulphur Marine Gas Oil (MGO) and Liquefied Natural gas (LNG)</p>	<p>Type: LNG tanker Total Main Power: 40MW (4 engines) Fuel (dual): Low sulphur Marine Gas Oil (MGO) and Liquefied Natural gas (LNG)</p>

Figure 2: The two types of ships to be included in the full chain cases [1]

Sleipnir uses LNG from its bunker tanks as fuel. The LNG needs to be vaporized to be used as fuel. The LNG carrier tanker uses boil off gas from the LNG cargo tanks (no vaporization needed), but this limits the cooling capacity available on the ship.

The Sleipnir case is representative for many ship types fuelled by LNG, e.g. cruise ships, container ships etc. The Total case study concerns a hypothetical new-build LNG carrier. This LNG carrier tanker case represents the fleet of such tankers, that consist of many hundreds of ships. With existing ships (approx. 700) and ordered ships (approx. 370) the number of LNG carrier tankers will exceed 1000 in near future [2]. Total has supplied operational profile for a sister vessel spanning 2 years of operational data at a daily average frequency.

The Sleipnir cases do not have the same regular voyage pattern as an LNG tanker on a route between e.g. Houston and Rotterdam. The Sleipnir will have a variety of tasks around the world. In average Sleipnir is in a port 8-10 times per year for bunkering. The cases for Sleipnir will be based on real data from a period of almost two years. The Sleipnir and LNG carrier tanker are described in more detail under the case descriptions. The document “TEA and LCA case study framework document for EverLoNG” is giving more details about the technical assumptions and the methodology for the TEA and LCA work.

Ports

The selection of ports is a result of work in the WPs.

The LNG tanker cases are related to shipping of LNG from North America to Europe. The voyage back and forth is covered.

The specific Ports selected are **Port of Houston** in Texas, USA and **Port of Rotterdam** in the Netherlands. Both ports have closeness to infrastructure for CCS. These Ports are also central for the regions.

Port of Houston

By total tonnage the Port of Houston is ranked as number one in the USA, with total tonnage of 266 million short tons in 2021 [3]. A large fraction of the tonnage is related to import and export of petroleum products and natural gas. There is infrastructure for handling of containers as well as LNG [4]. The proximity to the “Denbury Green Pipeline”, a pipeline for supply of CO₂ to Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR), connecting the Houston area to oil fields in Louisiana and Mississippi is also of importance.

Figure 3: View of Houston ship Channel from Buffalo Bayou Toll Bridge, Port of Houston (Photo: SINTEF K. Aas)

Port of Rotterdam

The Port of Rotterdam is by far the largest port by total tonnage in Europe, with approx. 425 million tonnes of goods handled (2022). Close to 50% is liquid bulk goods [5]. Infrastructure for LNG is in place. “Gate terminal” is the LNG import terminal of Rotterdam with a storage capacity of 180 000 m³ [6], and is located conveniently at the entrance or “gate” to the vast port area. Port of Rotterdam is also in the centre of the “Porthos project”, a CO₂ storage project just offshore of Rotterdam [7]. Rotterdam is also relatively close to other possible storage sites within the North Sea including the Norwegian Northern Lights storage project and the planned Aramis project offshore the Netherlands. Among the CCU opportunities is the production of green methanol. Port of Rotterdam is the largest methanol hub in north-western Europe and the top bunkering port in Europe for methanol for ships.

On- shore Equipment

Port facilities is part of the full chain cases. It is assumed that the CO₂ will be captured, processed, and liquefied on the vessel and offloaded from the ship to the onshore facility, for intermediate storage

and further processing. The deliverable D.2.1.1 “CO₂ offloading alternatives and guidelines” is describing the main facilities needed.

A drawing of the port's facilities that is needed for CO₂ and solvent handling is presented in Figure 4

Figure 4: Proposed port infrastructure.

Storage site

Several storage permanent storage sites have been developed or are under development in the North Sea basin. Early movers are the Northern Lights project and the Porthos project. The Aramis project is also under development. Due to available capacity, the Northern Lights Project and Aramis project are chosen as the storage sites in the full chain cases in EverLoNG.

- The Northern lights project (Norway) [8] is establishing a CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure at the west coast of Norway. First of a kind – open for third parties. Funding is 80% from the Norwegian Government. In the first phase the storage capacity will be 1.5 million tonnes CO₂ per year. The infrastructure will open in 2024 and offer storage to emitters in Norway and elsewhere in Europe. The second phase planned started in 2025 increases the storage capacity to 5 million tonnes per year. Total storage capacity is expected to be minimum 100 million tonnes.[9]

Recently (February 2024) the CO₂ specifications for storage at Northern lights has been adjusted. The changes are due to increased understanding of risks due to impurities [10]. The new specification can be found at Northern light web site (<https://norlights.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/Northern-Lights-GS-co2-Spec2024.pdf>). Main changes are much

smaller tolerance for mercury (Hg) content and for nitrogen oxides (NOx). Further, a list of more than 10 elements, with limits, are added to the specification.

- Porthos is a similar project in The Netherlands. Porthos stands for Port of Rotterdam CO₂ Transport Hub and Offshore Storage. It will provide storage capacity in an empty gas field just 20 km offshore of Rotterdam for the Industries located in the Rotterdam Port area. Capacity is expected to be 2,5 million tonnes per year over a 15-year period. The systems are planned to be operational in 2026. Even if the Porthos project is located perfectly with respect EverLoNG offloading of CO₂ in Rotterdam it is not likely as storage site since it is already fully booked [11].
- Aramis CCS [20] is another project aiming to support large scale CO₂ transport and storage service. This project can be an alternative to Northern lights when established after 2030. The project is a collaboration between TotalEnergies, Shell, EBN and Gasunie. The location is Rotterdam due to the proximity to industries and transport corridors. The plan is to establish a storage in offshore depleted gas fields with a capacity of 22Mt CO₂ per year. According to planned timeline, startup will be in 2028 or 2029, followed by an expansion phase after 2030. The total storage capacity is expected to be 400 Mt CO₂.
- Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) in the Gulf Coast Region in USA (Texas, Louisiana, Mississippi and Alabama). EOR has been used for many decades to increase the amount of oil that can be produced (recovered) over the lifespan of an oilfield [21]. The CO₂ is pumped into the reservoir to increase the pressure and hence enable prolonged production from the field. The long-term climate effect is debated. CO₂ is stored in the ground due to the injection, and if this CO₂ is captured from an industrial source or a ship it will contribute positively with respect to climate emissions. At the same time more fossil fuel is produced leading to CO₂ emissions when combusted.

Utilization

The full chain utilization cases (case 2 a, b and 4 a, b) differ from the storage cases (case 1 a, b and 3 a, b) only by different routing of the CO₂ when offloaded in the European port selected, Rotterdam. Instead of being shipped to permanent storage through the Northern Lights project or Aramis project the captured CO₂ is transported to a plant where the CO₂ can be reused in a product that is offered to the market. Such recycling needs to be a climate viable alternative to the fossil-based product as well as having an economically potential. CCU might lower the net cost of CO₂ reduction to the atmosphere by offering a product to the market.

Several routes for utilizing of captured CO₂ can be outlined [12]. However, there are challenges associated with bringing CO₂ into the feedstock due to, high energy demand and price on renewable energy, lack of established market, technology challenges and lack of regulatory framework.

Synthetic fuels are among the products where CCU finds a potential. If fuels that are currently in use could be produced in a circular way by utilizing captured CO₂ and renewable energy sources, it will be a step towards carbon neutrality. Methane and Methanol are products that can be produced from CO₂ and hydrogen. The hydrogen needs to be “green hydrogen”, that is produced with water electrolysis powered by renewable electricity. Methane and Methanol can both be used as fuel and as feedstock for products. Existing infrastructure for natural gas and methanol distribution can be

utilized. Methane and methanol are versatile chemicals with numerous industrial applications. Methane can be used for heating, electricity generation, transportation, and as a feedstock for various chemical processes. Methanol is used in the production of plastics, paints, adhesives, and fuels. This versatility enhances the market potential of e-methane and e-methanol.

Methanol is among the most common industrial chemicals in the world with yearly production exceeding 100 million tonnes after year 2020 [15]. Methanol is used both as a material (70%) and an energy source/fuel (30%)[16].

Methanol is among the products several sources mention as a viable for CCU. Several sources suggest MeOH targeted for the regulated transport market as the best pathway for short term opportunities for increasing the CO₂ demand in the CCU market. E-methanol produced by renewable energy has a higher cost of 18-25 €/GJ compared to a cost of 10-15 €/GJ for MeOH based on fossil fuel production[13].

The global marine fuel demand was estimated to be in the order of 500 000 000 ton/year [14] in 2020. Converting the CO₂ captured from the ships into E-methanol in a plant close to a port may form an interesting lifecycle opportunity as the shipping and logistics company Maersk among others investigates the opportunity for E-methanol production for ship fuel.

Current methanol production methods

There are several processes and raw materials available for the production methanol. Most commonly is steam reforming of natural gas to create synthesis gas. The synthesis gas is fed into a reactor with a catalyst, resulting in production of methanol and water [17]. Feedstocks may also come from biomass or coal. In a life cycle perspective, the carbon footprint of methanol varies very much with feedstock and production pathway. The resulting carbon footprint can result in negative carbon emissions (-50 to -100 g CO₂eq/MJ) for feedstocks from biomethane (anaerobe digestion of cow and pig manure). Fossil feedstocks result currently in emissions in the range of approx. 100 g CO₂eq/MJ (from natural gas) to as high as 300 g CO₂eq/MJ (from coal)[18][19].

E-methanol is based on green hydrogen (hydrogen from water electrolysis with renewable electricity) and captured CO₂, can have a low carbon footprint ,provided the electricity comes from renewable sources (PV, wind, hydro)[18][19].

The defined full chain cases

The cases from ship type and operation to CO₂ storage or utilization are summarized graphically in Figure 5 to Figure 12.

- Case 1: Sleipnir CO₂ storage pathway
- Case 2: Sleipnir CO₂ utilization pathway
- Case 3: LNG tanker CO₂ storage pathway
- Case 4: LNG tanker CO₂ utilization pathway

Sleipnir cases

The Sleipnir cases, storage or utilization are equal during the vessel's operation at sea and SBCC is ongoing. The difference between cases, Case 1 and Case 2 is that the captured CO₂ is routed differently when offloaded on Port and transported to its destination either for permanent storage or for CCU. The CO₂ volume captured for each trip (6 weeks) is expected to be approx. 4500 tCO₂.

LNG tanker cases

It is assumed that this LNG tanker ship will transport LNG from port of Houston to the port of Rotterdam, and the journey takes 11 days one way. CO₂ is captured during the transport and offloaded when in port. The difference between cases, Case 3 and Case 4, is that the captured CO₂ is routed differently when offloaded in port in Europe, either for permanent storage or for CCU. The CO₂ volume captured for each trip from US to Europe is expected to be approx. 2500 tCO₂ and 2400 tCO₂ on the return journey.

Case 1: Sleipnir CO₂ Storage Pathways.

Case 1a. Sleipnir SBCC Operation to CO₂ Storage Pathway, Northern Lights.

The ship will be offshore for 6 weeks, before it will enter the Port of Rotterdam. Then the CO₂ will be offloaded by flexible hoses and stored in intermediate tanks at the port. The CO₂ will be loaded into CO₂ ships that will transport the CO₂ to the Northern Lights terminal at Øygarden before the CO₂ is transported in pipelines to the final storage place in the North Sea.

- Sleipnir operation 6 weeks – with SBCC – average approx. 4500 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Rotterdam.
- Treatment (if any) and intermediate storage in Rotterdam.
- Export and transport by ship to, Øygarden, Norway.
- Pipeline transportation.
- CO₂ storage in the formations in the North Sea (**Northern Lights project**)

Figure 5 : Case 1a. Sleipnir SBCC Operation to CO₂ Storage Pathway, Northern Lights.

Case 1b. Sleipnir SBCC Operation to CO₂ Storage Pathway, Aramis.

The ship will be offshore for 6 weeks, before it will enter the Port of Rotterdam. Then the CO₂ will be offloaded by flexible hoses and stored in intermediate tanks at the port. Thereafter it will be transferred to the Aramis collection hub, before the CO₂ is transported in pipelines to the final storage place in the North Sea.

- Sleipnir operation 6 weeks – with SBCC – average approx. 4500 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Rotterdam.
- Export to **Aramis** collection hub.
- Transport by subsea pipeline offshore.
- CO₂ storage in the formations in the North Sea (**Aramis**)

Figure 6: Case 1b. Sleipnir SBCC Operation to CO₂ Storage Pathway, Aramis.

Case 2: Sleipnir CO₂ Utilization Pathways.

Case 2a. Sleipnir SBCC Operation to CO₂ Utilization Pathway, Methanol.

The ship will be offshore for 6 weeks, before it will enter the Port of Rotterdam. Then the CO₂ will be offloaded by flexible hoses and stored in intermediate tanks at the port. The CO₂ will be transported by pipeline, train or truck to a **methanol** plant located in Port of Rotterdam area

- Sleipnir operation 6 weeks – with SBCC – average approx. 4500 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Rotterdam.
- Treatment (if any) and intermediate storage in Rotterdam.
- Transport by pipeline or truck to a **methanol** plant located in Port of Rotterdam area.

Figure 7: Case 2a. Sleipnir SBCC Operation to CO₂ Utilization Pathway, Methanol.

Case 2b. Sleipnir SBCC Operation to CO₂ Utilization Pathway, Methane.

The ship will be offshore for 6 weeks, before it will enter the Port of Rotterdam. Then the CO₂ will be offloaded by flexible hoses and stored in intermediate tanks at the port. The CO₂ will be transported by pipeline, train or truck to a **methane** plant located in Port of Rotterdam area.

- Sleipnir operation 6 weeks – with SBCC – average approx. 4500 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Rotterdam
- Treatment (if any) and intermediate storage in Rotterdam
- Transport by pipeline or truck to a **methane** plant located in Port of Rotterdam area.

Figure 8: Case 2b. Sleipnir SBCC Operation to CO₂ Utilization Pathway, Methane.

Case 3: LNG tanker CO₂ Storage Pathways.

Case 3a. LNG Tanker SBCC Operation to CO₂ Storage Pathway, Northern Lights.

The CO₂ captured on the ship during transport to the port of Rotterdam will be offloaded there by flexible hoses. The CO₂ is stored intermediate in tanks at the port before the CO₂ is transported by ship to Øygarden for further pipeline transport to the reservoir in the North Sea.

After the return trip CO₂ is offloaded by flexible hoses at Port of Houston and stored in intermediate storage tanks before it is compressed and transported by pipeline to an EOR reservoir.

- LNG transport from Houston 11 days – with SBCC – average approx. 2500 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Rotterdam
- Treatment (if any) and intermediate storage in Rotterdam
- Transport by ship to, Øygarden, Norway
- Pipeline transportation.
- CO₂ storage in the formations in the North Sea (Northern Lights project)
- LNG ship return to Houston (empty) 11 days -with SBCC average approx. 2400 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Houston
- Intermediate storage
- Transport by pipeline to EOR reservoir

Figure 9: Case 3a. LNG Tanker SBCC Operation to CO₂ Storage Pathway, Northern Lights.

Case 3b. LNG Tanker SBCC Operation to CO₂ Storage Pathway, Aramis.

The CO₂ captured on the ship during transport to the port of Rotterdam will be offloaded there by flexible hoses. The CO₂ is stored intermediate in tanks at the port before the CO₂ is transported by to Aramis collection hub, for further pipeline transport to the reservoir in the North Sea.

After the return trip CO₂ is offloaded by flexible hoses at Port of Houston and stored in intermediate storage tanks before it is compressed and transported by pipeline to an EOR reservoir.

- LNG transport from Houston 11 days – with SBCC – average approx. 2500 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Rotterdam
- Treatment (if any) and intermediate storage in Rotterdam
- Transfer to **Aramis** Collection HUB
- Pipeline transportation.
- CO₂ storage in the formations in the North Sea (**Aramis**)
- LNG ship return to Houston (empty) 11 days -with SBCC average approx. 2400 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Houston
- Intermediate storage
- Transport by pipeline to EOR reservoir

Figure 10: Case 3b. LNG Tanker SBCC Operation to CO₂ Storage Pathway, Aramis.

Case 4: LNG tanker CO₂ Utilization Pathways.

Case 4a. LNG Tanker SBCC Operation to CO₂ Utilization Pathway, Methanol.

The CO₂ captured on the ship during transport to the port of Rotterdam will be offloaded there by flexible hoses. The CO₂ is stored intermediate in tanks at the port before pipeline, train or truck transport to a **methanol** plant located in Port of Rotterdam area.

After the return trip the CO₂ is offloaded by flexible hoses at Port of Houston and stored in intermediate storage tanks before it is compressed and transported by pipeline to an EOR reservoir.

- LNG transport from Houston 11 days – with SBCC – average approx. 2500 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Rotterdam
- Treatment (if any) and intermediate storage in Rotterdam
- Transport by pipeline or truck to a **methanol** plant located in Port of Rotterdam area.
- LNG ship return to Houston (empty) 11 days -with SBCC average approx. 2400 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Houston
- Intermediate storage
- Transport by pipeline to EOR reservoir

Figure 11: Case 4a. LNG Tanker SBCC Operation to CO₂ Utilization Pathway, Methanol.

Case 4b. LNG Tanker SBCC Operation to CO₂ Utilization Pathway, Methane.

The CO₂ captured on the ship during transport to the port of Rotterdam will be offloaded there by flexible hoses. The CO₂ is stored intermediate in tanks at the port before transport by pipeline, train or truck to a **methane** plant located in Port of Rotterdam area.

After the return trip the CO₂ is offloaded by flexible hoses at Port of Houston and stored in intermediate storage tanks before it is compressed and transported by pipeline to an EOR reservoir.

- LNG transport from Houston 11 days – with SBCC – average approx. 2500 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Rotterdam
- Treatment (if any) and intermediate storage in Rotterdam
- Transport by pipeline or truck to a **methane** plant located in Port of Rotterdam area.
- LNG ship return to Houston (empty) 11 days -with SBCC average approx. 2400 tCO₂/voyage captured.
- Unloading of the CO₂ in Houston
- Intermediate storage
- Transport by pipeline to EOR reservoir

Figure 12: Case 4b. LNG Tanker SBCC Operation to CO₂ Utilization Pathway, Methane.

Conclusion

Full chain cases are defined and described above.

- Case 1a and 1b: Sleipnir CO₂ storage pathways
- Case 2a and 2b: Sleipnir CO₂ utilization pathways
- Case 3a and 3b: LNG tanker CO₂ storage pathways
- Case 4a and 4b: LNG tanker CO₂ utilization pathways

The defined cases will be evaluated by life cycle analysis (LCA) and techno-economic assessments (TEA) in WP4

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